

2035, dull 2077, and IR36. Lysine per seed was highest in dull 2035, followed by dull 2077, dull EM47 and ae and IR36. Fat content was high in sugary and shrunken grains.

All mutants except ae had lower

apparent amylose content in brown rice than IR36. Gelatinization temperature (GT) of the samples were intermediate except for dull EM47 and ae.

The extremely high GT value for the sugary mutant may be due to the effect

of its high sucrose level on GT.

Corresponding starch mutants based on Kinmaze showed similar trends in starch properties. A sample of the ae mutant of Kinmaze had 31 % apparent amylose in defatted brown rice. □

Quality characteristics of some new aromatic rices

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We compared milling and cooking performance of 13 aromatic rice lines and Basmati 370. All samples were

grown under similar environmental conditions and tested 2 mo after hand harvesting.

Brown rice recovery varied widely (see table). All lines except NIRRI-PTB-11 and NIRRI-PTB-138 (PL) had higher brown rice yields than Basmati 370; NIRRI-PTB-22 had the highest yield. Head rice yield of NIRRI-PTB-22 was also highest. NIRRI-PTB-140 had more

than 40% broken. NIRRI-1-10643-1-65 had exceptionally long grains. Three lines had higher length:breadth ratios (L/B) than Basmati 370. Six lines had amylose as high as or higher than that of Basmati 370.

Cooked NIRRI-PTB-140-6 had the highest LB, followed by NIRRI-PTB-138 (PL). The elongation ratio of S41 was higher than that of Basmati 370. □

Milling and cooking characteristics of some aromatic rices. Ludhiana, India.

Variety or line	Milling recovery (% of rough rice)			Milled rice					
	Brown rice	Milled rice	Head rice	Protein (%)	Amylose (%)	Length of raw rice (mm)	Length:breadth		Elongation ratio ^a
							Raw rice	Cooked rice	
NIRRI-PTB-11	76.1	70.0	55.0	9.7	21.7	6.7	3.94	3.88	1.45
NIRRI-PTB-20	78.3	72.0	47.0	8.5	26.3	6.7	3.53	3.36	1.25
NIRRI-PTB-22	80.4	74.0	64.2	9.2	19.9	6.8	3.40	3.60	1.32
NIRRI-PTB-23	78.4	72.1	55.7	8.8	19.0	6.6	3.88	3.64	1.38
NIRRI-PTB-36	79.9	73.5	41.9	9.4	24.5	6.7	3.19	3.58	1.39
NIRRI-PTB-138 (PL)	77.5	71.3	47.7	9.8	18.1	7.7	4.05	4.42	1.38
NIRRI-PTB-138 (MS)	74.7	68.7	50.8	8.3	17.2	7.5	3.95	3.75	1.20
NIRRI-PTB-140	78.9	72.6	32.5	9.6	16.3	7.5	4.17	4.21	1.35
NIRRI-PTB-140-6	78.8	72.5	54.1	9.6	15.4	7.9	4.65	4.50	1.37
NIRRI-PTB-145	80.2	73.8	54.6	10.2	12.7	7.3	4.29	3.88	1.38
NIRRI-PTB-170	79.4	73.0	47.8	9.4	18.1	6.9	3.29	3.76	1.36
S41	79.9	73.5	43.5	9.0	19.0	7.0	3.89	4.07	1.57
NIRRI-1-106-4-3-1-65	79.5	73.1	48.7	8.4	18.1	8.3	4.61	4.03	1.46
Basmati 370	78.0	71.7	42.6	9.8	19.0	7.7	4.28	4.37	1.53
Mean	78.6	72.2	49.4	9.3	18.9	7.2	3.97	3.93	1.39

^aLength of cooked milled rice ÷ length of raw rice.

Disease resistance

Sources of multiple resistance to rice blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB) in Nepal

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Rice BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*

and BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* have been observed widely in the tropical and subtropical regions of Nepal, the country's major rice-producing areas. Breeding for varieties with multiple resistance to these diseases would be easier and quicker using sources with multiple resistance.

To identify such sources, varietal reactions to BI and BB in Kankai,

Sources of multiple resistance to rice BI and BB in Nepal, 1985-87.^a

Variety	Reaction to BI		Reaction to BB	
	Average	Range	Average	Range
Janaki	2.3	0.0-3.0	1.5	0.0-3.0
Laxmi	2.1	0.0-3.0	2.4	1.5-3.0
KAU1727	1.7	0.0-3.0	3.1	3.0-3.4

^aScoring according to *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale: 0-9. ^bScored 21 d after inoculation.